

Soil Quality Assessment in Dehradun District

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Abstract: Soil harbours mixture of various organic and inorganic nutrients which supports the land plants but the multifarious activities of human pollutes it. The physicochemical study of soil parameters is important for plant growth and soil management. The present work is thus attempted to evaluate physico chemical parameters of soil samples to assess its quality. Four representative samples in triplicate were obtained and analyzed for its colour, texture, moisture content, organic carbon content, TDS, pH, EC, Ca^{+2} , Mg^{+2} , Cl. Results show that most of soils were little alkaline having pH ranged from 7.6-8.1 except site 2 where pH 5.1 was observed. The value of electrical conductivity ranged between 0.30-0.73 μ .S/cm indicating the normal nature of soil. Moreover, the soils were having organic carbon ranging between 0.31%-0.80%. The Ca^{+2} , Mg^{+2} content ranged between 35.3-66.3mg/l while Cl ranged between 30.1-38.3 mg/l. This information will be beneficial for environmentalists to assess the factors responsible for the variation of soil parameters in different sites and to the farmers to evaluate the fertility and nutrient status of the soil for precise farming and agricultural management.

Key Words: Soil analysis, pH, physico chemical properties, moisture content, organic carbon.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Soil is an unconsolidated material of the earth's crust in which land plants can grow well provided water and temperature is adequate, enough minerals are available and toxic substances are in low concentrations. Soil has fragile ecosystem [1,2]. Approximately the soil contains 50-60% mineral matter, 25-35% water, 15-25% air and little percentage of organic matter [3]. Time to time evaluation of the physico-chemical parameters of soil is important to inherent soil fertility status to sustain productivity. [4,5]. Physico chemical analysis of soil and rain water samples is said to determine the quality and extent of pollution [6]. Lot of research has been done in the analysis of macronutrients nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium (NPK) in soil [7, 8] but analysis of other parameters are equally important. Present study is focused on studying the physico-chemical parameters of the soil collected from different areas of dehradun district. Twelve samples were collected from four sites of the dehradun district and its physico-chemical analysis have been performed to know its different parameters like color, texture, moisture content, total carbon content, conductivity, Total dissolved solids (TDS), Chloride (Cl⁻), Calcium (Ca^{+2}), Magnesium (Mg^{+2}).

2. MATERIALS :

Area of Study

Study area selected is Dehradun district which is one of the most important districts of Uttarakhand. It is located between the between 29° 58' and 31° 2'30" north latitudes and 77° 34'45" and 78° 18'30" east longitudes covering the area of 3,088 km². Study was conducted in dehradun district of Uttarakhand state. The locations were Selaqui and Herbertpur. Selaqui is a developing Industrial area. Herbertpur is a town located on the bank on river Asan at the border of Uttarakhand and Himachal Pradesh.

Table 1: Sampling Sites

Site No	Site Name	Type of Land	Location
1	Selaqui-I	Agricultural field	Maya group of colleges
2	Herbertpur-I	Tea estate	Atan bagh
3	Herbertpur-II	Asan River bank	Asan barrage
4	Selaqui-II	Industrial area	Sidcul Industrial area

All the samples were collected by the standard method of sampling. The method used was V shape method in which 15 cm plot was dug in V shape and approximately ½ kg of the soil samples were collected in a sterile polythene bags. Collected samples were transferred to laboratory under sterile conditions. For soil nutrients and physico-chemical analysis, samples were air dried and sieved. For determining moisture content the soil was sieved, weighed and then air dried. Soil samples were suspended in distilled water (1:4 w/v) and the suspension was stirred constantly for half an hour and kept undisturbed for 15 minutes.

The chemicals and reagents used for analysis were of A.R. grade.

3. METHOD :

Table 2: Analysis Method

S. No	Parameter	Method	Equipment
1	Conductivity $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$	Electrometric	Conductometer
2	pH	pH metric	pH meter
3	Calcium ions mg/l	Complexometric titration	Titrimetric set up
4	Magnesium ions mg/l	Complexometric titration	Titrimetric set up
5	Total Ca^{+2} Mg^{+2} mg/l	Complexometric titration	Titrimetric set up
6	Alkalinity mg/l	Titration with Sulphuric acid	Titrimetric set up
7	TDS mg/l	Electrometric	Conductometer
8	Organic carbon	Walkley and Black method	Titrimetric set up
9	Moisture content	Gravimetric determination	Oven
10	Cl^-	Precipitation titration	Titrimetric set up

3.1. Analytical Techniques

3.1.1. pH - A pH meter (Electronics India) having readability of 0.01 was used for the measurement. 5g of soil sample was mixed with distilled water and kept in a shaker for 30 minutes. Solutions were allowed to settle for 5 minutes and pH was measured.

3.1.2. Moisture content -10 g of soil were oven dried and weight loss was recorded.

3.1.3. Conductivity- Electrical Conductivity of the soil was measured by conductometer (Popular traders) using filtrate of the soil extract and 0.01 M KCl solutions as standard reference.

3.1.4 . Ca^{+2} , Mg^{+2} ions were determined by complexometric method using EDTA as standard solution and EBT as an indicator.

3.1.5. TDS -Total dissolved solids refers to any salts, minerals, metals, cations, or anions which are dissolved in a soil saturation extract. The total concentration of the soluble salts in soil can be measured by the EC of the soil solution.

3.1.6 .Chloride was determined by Argentometric method using standard 0.01N AgNO_3 solution and 5% Potassium chromate solution was added as an indicator.

3.1.7 % Organic carbon (OC) content was determined by using Walkley and Black method [9] with chromic acid wet digestion using diphenylamine indicator.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION :

Physico chemical properties of soil samples were studied and summarized in Table 3

Table 3: RESULT

S. No.	Parameter	Site1	Site 2	Site 3	Site 4
1	Colour	Wood Grey	Dark Grey	Grey	Grey
2	Texture	Sandy+ clayey	Clayey	Sandy	Sandy
3	Moisture content (%)	13.05±0.02	22.18±0.02	11.11±0.01	10.23±0.01
3	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	0.478±0.002	0.732±0.003	0.303±0.001	0.431±0.001
4	pH	7.4±0.10	5.1±0.00	8.1±0.20	7.8±0.00

5	Calcium ions mg/l	64.5±0.12	61.3±0.16	66.3±0.22	54.3±0.10
6	Magnesium ions mg/l	44.6±0.11	35.5±0.12	47.1±0.11	48.3±0.30
7	Total Ca ⁺² and Mg ⁺² mg/l	109.1±0.2	96.8±0.1	113.4±0.2	102.6±0.2
8	TDS mg/l	139.4±1.1	143.4±0.8	156.3±0.2	170.0±0.4
9	Chloride mg/l	38.3±0.1	30.1±0.2	33.2±0.2	36.5±0.1
10	% C (OC)	0.40±0.0	0.58±0.1	0.39±0.1	0.38±0.1

4.1 pH - Soil pH is considered a master variable as it controls physical, chemical, biological properties as well as the mineral nutrient soil quality and microorganism activity. [10]. Soil should have correct balance of acid and alkali. The pH range of 6.8 to 8.0 has been recommended optimum for plants growth. The pH of soil samples in above study shows variation 5.1 to 8.1. Low pH i.e. 5.1 was noted from the soil sample collected from site 2 which is a tea estate and having humid surroundings and clayey soil.

Site 1, 3, 4 was showing soil having alkaline pH which may be attributed to its sandy texture and low moisture content. Alkaline soils are characterized by high concentrations of carbonates (CO₃²⁻) and bicarbonates (HCO₃⁻) which have acid neutralizing capacity. [11]

Alkalinity stress in most of the plants have resulted in stunted growth due to poor nutrient uptake and leaf chlorosis due to high and low uptake of Na⁺ and Fe⁺² respectively [12].

4.2. Moisture content- Soil moisture is indicator of richness of soil as it has deep impact in soil microbial activity thus enhancing organic carbon content. [13] Results shows maximum moisture content of 22.18% at site 2 and minimum moisture content of 10.23% at site 4.

4.3. Soil Texture - Soil textures refer to the relative proportion of different soil particles i.e. sand, clay and silt. Site 1, 3, 4 reported sandy textures while site 2 reported clayey texture.

4.4. Conductivity- The electrical conductivity of a soil solution increases with the increased concentration of ions. Study of collected soil samples shows variation in conductivity values between 0.303 μ.S/cm to 0.732 μ.S/cm thus suggesting normal soil. Low EC may be attributed to presence of sandy soil with low organic matter while high EC is shown in clayey soil. Conductivity of soil gives a suggestion on the quantity of fertilizers to be applied in soil.

4.5. Ca⁺², Mg⁺² - Calcium is essential for root health, growth of new roots and root hairs, and the development of leaves while Magnesium is a key component of chlorophyll, the green coloring material of plants, and is vital for photosynthesis. [14,15]. The concentration of calcium varied from 54.3 to 66.3 mg/l while the concentration of magnesium varied from 35.5 to 48.3 mg/l.

4.6. TDS - it indicates soil salinity. The increased occurrence of salt in soil significantly impacts the environment, mainly degrading crop productivity and soil quality by reducing the ability of crops and plants to take up water and leading to lower yields, which are responsible for serious economic losses in agricultural production . It varied from 139-170 mg/l.

4.7. Chloride -Natural inputs of chlorine (Cl) to soils come mainly from rainwater, sea spray, dust and air pollution. In addition, human practices, such as irrigation and fertilization, contribute significantly to Chloride deposition. In the soil solution, Chlorine occurs predominantly as the chloride anion (Cl⁻).Chloride concentration in the given soil samples ranged between 30.1±0.02 to 38.3±0.02 mg/l.

4.8. %Organic carbon (OC) - Percentage of carbon varies from 0.43 to 0.59 which shows normal soil. Soils in low organic carbon are possibly because of high temperature and good aeration in the soil which increased the rate of oxidation of organic matter.

5. CONCLUSION :

The present study reveals that the soil quality of all the four sites was better and safe. Variations observed can be due to urbanization and industrialization. For maintaining sustainable soil health the analysis study carried out will be helpful.

6. RECOMMENDATION :

From the observed data and its interpretation study it is suggested that periodic monitoring of soil parameters will be helpful in preventing the contamination and mineral deficiency.

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